

Instructional Practices of EFL Teachers in Relation to Students' English Performance

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Abstract:

Amidst the government's efforts, the English communicative competence of students in Vietnam has yet to see immense progress. Mark. A. Ashwill, an American educator who served as country director of the Institute of International Education (IIE), said two key reasons preventing Vietnamese students from being fluent in English are "how English is taught and a lack of learner motivation" (Nga, 2020). Therefore, this study aimed to determine the levels of instructional practices of EFL teachers about the Stage 6 students' English performance. To achieve this aim, the researcher used a sample of 85 teachers and an average of 30 students per teacher in a private school in a country in Southeast Asia during the first term of the 2022-2023 school year. The researcher used the descriptive-correlational method of research, which used a researcher-made questionnaire as the primary data-gathering technique. The result of Spearman rho on the relationship between the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers and the English performance of Stage 6 students is 0.108 with a p-value of 0.327 and -0.021 with a p-value of 0.845 interpreted as "not significant." The result of this study, calls for further study in a different areas that were not included and follow up studies covering more teachers, not limited to one school, but include different schools and language centers, to validate the results.

Keywords: Instructional practices, EFL Teachers, students' performance, assessment of learning, ICT integration, differentiated instructions

Introduction:

Nature of Problem

The world has become more interdependent, and expanding relations with countries increases the need to speak a foreign language (UNG, 2023). As years pass, many countries use English as their official language, thus making it the most widely spoken language globally and now approximately used by over 1.35 billion people. As English grows, global culture has created an atmosphere where all can communicate and understand one another's culture. In Vietnam, the Ministry of Education has been thriving in recent years to integrate English education into the regional and global arena (Ngozwana, 2020). According to the Ministry of Education and Training (MOET) in Circular No. 32 (dated 26 December 2018), English is compulsory in the general education curriculum from grades 3 to 12. However, making English as the second official language in the country requires a constitutional amendment (Sen, 2018).

The country's general English language curriculum is built with the view that communicative competencies are the targets of the teaching process (MOET, 2023). However, learners and educators blame the lack of investment in training teachers and that English programs in public schools are outdated and irrelevant (Nga, 2020). With this, the government invested in professional development training for teachers to improve students' English performance. This response accords with one of the studies that states that the quality of education and student achievement are closely related to teachers' professional development (Sevim & Akin, 2021). English is Vietnam's most popular foreign language, and many Vietnamese students attend English classes at language centers. Some parents hired private tutors and online English teachers to teach their children at home. Big and small cities in Vietnam have many foreign language centers serving students mainly in the evening after students finish school. However, many Vietnamese students still need to learn to use English to communicate with foreigners.

With this, the researcher is eager to investigate the undermining factors that affect the English students' English proficiency. This research would like to determine whether the level of EFL teachers' professional development and instructional practices are accounted for as antecedents of impeding students' English performance. After intensive reading, only a few studies have been conducted on the influence of teachers' professional development and instructional practices on students' English performance, specifically in this Southeast Asian country. The results of this study will be the basis for coming up with possible solutions to improve

the current situation. The findings of this study will serve as the cornerstone for coming up with innovative solutions to enhance the present situation.

Current State of Knowledge

In recent years, Vietnam has undergone significant changes in the field of English as a foreign language education, aimed at enhancing the quality of education and fostering socio-economic development within the country. These changes also facilitate greater regional and global international engagement for Vietnam. Despite heightened efforts and investment from both the government and individuals, Vietnam's English language education system is still falling short of expectations. The country's current teaching practices are hindered by many obstacles, including overcrowded classrooms, inadequate resources, outdated materials, and a focus on rote memorization for exams rather than practical language skills. Additionally, teachers are overwhelmed, and students need more motivation and opportunities to practice and apply their English skills in real-life situations (Le, 2019).

Prominent researchers have identified Assessment for Learning as a powerful classroom assessment approach that places students at the forefront of the learning process. By recognizing students as active participants in their learning journey, Assessment for Learning not only enhances student engagement but also holds the potential to revolutionize traditional teaching and assessment methods (Liu & Xiu, 2017). Differentiated instruction is another effective instructional practice that has been found effective in some studies. Differentiated instructions are designed with diverse variations to adjust the teaching-learning process to the different characteristics of the students. Because classrooms can be composed of students with different abilities—commonly known as mixed-ability classrooms—it has been observed that their differences affect their readiness to learn a foreign language, affecting their participation in teaching and learning success (Suwastini, 2021).

In the modern era of globalization, the English language has risen to prominence as the official language of the world and a key tool for international communication. According to Rao (2016), possessing a strong command of English has become essential to a compelling persona, as it is widely utilized for intercultural interactions. For non-native English speakers, honing proficiency in the language is crucial for effective communication. This can be achieved through a focus on both comprehension and composition skills. One key aspect of mastering English is accurately reproducing accented or stressed sounds, which contributes to clear and articulate speech. However, perhaps the most critical element of language proficiency lies in vocabulary knowledge, as a rich and varied vocabulary enables individuals to express themselves precisely and nuance. In today's educational landscape, English holds equal importance to traditional academic disciplines, underscoring its significance in preparing individuals for success in a globalized world.

Throughout the last few decades, researchers in many nations have studied the learning demands of English students, particularly those who do not speak English. Nguyen & Habok (2021) stated that most people in the study of Vietnamese said that they need English because they plan to use it for future employment and cross-cultural and national communications. They also want to practice their speaking and listening skills more than their other English skills. However, the students' English practices in the classroom do not allow them to practice these skills as much as they need. English proficiency among students in academic settings should be high to be effective. This will help them in many ways, but they are usually given limited opportunities to use these skills in academic settings. However, Vietnamese English language teachers, who are teaching English in their schools, must develop their language skills. They must practice their skills to help their students develop English proficiency. This is very important because they can effectively teach the language if they can proficiently socialize with others using the second language.

A recent study conducted by Melvina and Julia (2021) found that various factors, including technical, psychological, and political influences, had a positive and significant impact on students' English proficiency levels. Interestingly, the sociocultural factor was the only variable that did not show any effect based on the study results. This suggests that educators and students should strongly emphasize the concept of learner autonomy in their journey to enhance English language skills. By taking control of their learning process, students can actively engage in regular practice and training sessions, seeking consistent teacher feedback to facilitate improvement. Emphasizing the importance of self-directed learning and encouraging a proactive approach to language acquisition can lead to more effective and sustainable progress in mastering English.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored on the Practice Theory by Theodore Schatzki, and the Performance Theory by John Sweller.

This study is anchored on Practice Theory by Theodore Schatzki. Similar to all theories of social practice, Schatzki's web page ontology is based on the presumption that each social phenomenon is rooted in practices. However, in contrast to other practice theorists, Schatzki assumes that there is only one single level of social reality: the level of social practices (Seidl & Whittington, 2014). This theory highlights that practices and material arrangements are always connected and tend to change over time. For example, video conferencing technology has affected meeting practices, and the introduction of new teaching methods has an impact on the current teaching strategies. According to Schatzki (2013), the different ways practice-arrangement bundles evolve have one thing in common: new practical understandings must emerge to consolidate the change.

This theory is significant to the study as it emphasizes that teachers' instructional practices are not fixed; they are constantly evolving and subject to change. This theory encourages a shift from a traditional, rigid curriculum to a more flexible and adaptive instructional approach that recognizes learners' diverse needs, interests, and backgrounds. Educators can move beyond viewing teaching and learning as isolated events and instead recognize them as ongoing practices shaped by various factors such as social norms, cultural influences, and institutional structures.

Another theory that supports this study is Performance Theory by Richard Schechner. Schechner's performance theory is a multidisciplinary approach that examines the nature and significance of human performance in various cultural and social contexts. According to Schechner, performance is not limited to artistic or theatrical events but encompasses all human actions and behaviors. He emphasizes that performance is a social phenomenon that involves the interplay between performers, spectators, and the surrounding context. He envisages 'performing in everyday life' as a central aspect of performativity. 'Performativity is everywhere – in daily behavior, in the professions, on the internet and media, in the arts and the language.' His theory emphasizes that performance is not limited to the stage but can be found in various aspects of our lives (UKEssays, 2018).

This theory is significant to the study because it emphasizes that teachers should incorporate more experiential and embodied learning approaches that improve students' English performance. Students should actively engage in performances and role-playing activities to deepen their understanding of the language and build a connection to the subject or skill being developed. In the classroom, teachers can incorporate performance-based assessments to assess students' English knowledge and ability to apply it creatively in real-world contexts.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers concerning Stage 6 students' English performance in a private school in a Southeast Asian country during the first term of the 2022-2023 school year. Specifically, this study sought to examine the following questions: 1) the level of EFL teachers' instructional practices in terms of assessment of learning, ICT integration, and differentiated instructions; 2) level of English performance of Stage 6 students during the first term for the school year 2022-2023; 3) the significant difference in the level of EFL teachers' instructional practices when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; and 4) the significant relationship between the level of EFL teachers' instructional practices and the English performance of Stage 6 students.

Methodology

The researcher is guided by the methodology employed in this study. This includes the research design, the locale of the study where it is conducted, and the respondents. The data-gathering instruments and procedures, validity, reliability, analytical schemes, and statistical tools are also described.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive research design to determine the levels of instructional practices of EFL teachers in relation to the English performance of Stage 6 students in a private school in a country in Southeast Asia for the school year 2022-2023. Descriptive research is a study technique that describes the traits of the populace or phenomenon that is being studied. It means observing and measuring without manipulating variables (Mc Combes, 2019). Researchers use it to gather information about a particular group or phenomenon. This type of research provides a detailed and accurate picture of the characteristics and behavior of a specific population or subject. By observing and collecting data about a specific topic, descriptive research helps researchers gain a deeper understanding of a specific problem and provide valuable insights that can inform future studies.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were 85 secondary and high school EFL teachers on different campuses of a private school in a country in Southeast Asia. The number of respondents was manageable, so purposive sampling was utilized. Purposive sampling is also known as selective sampling because this method deliberately chooses participants based on the researcher's judgment (Stewart, 2024). Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents.

Instruments

A self-made instrument was used to gather baseline data for the study. It was subjected to validity (4.732-excellent) and reliability (0.778-Acceptable). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good, respectively. It was composed of two (2) parts. Part I was on the respondents' profiles, such as length of service, highest educational attainment, age, and sex. Part II contained items on the level of EFL teachers' instructional practices in the assessment of learning, ICT Integration, and differentiated instructions. Each consisted of six (7) items that were measured using the following scale (modified Likert's scale): (5) Always, (4) Often, (3) Sometimes, (2) Rarely, and (1) Almost never. The English performance data were the first-term grades of the stage 6 students in a Southeast Asian country. The students' grades were retrieved from individual teachers chosen as respondents to the study.

Data-Gathering Procedure

In order to collect the data, an email was sent to the school's Human Resource Team to allow the researcher to collect data from the target respondents. When a positive response was received, the researcher started conducting the survey. The survey was in Google Forms and sent individually to the study respondents. English performance data was retrieved from EFL teachers who were respondents to the study. The data was the first-term assessment grades of the students in the school year 2022-2023. Once all the respondents responded, the data was tabulated using appropriate statistical tools.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers in terms of learning assessment, ICT integration, and differentiated instructions. Objective No. 2 likewise used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of English performance of Stage 6 students. Objective No. 3 also used the comparative analytical scheme and the Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Objective 4 also used the relational analytical scheme and Spearman rho to determine the significant relationship between the level of instructional practices of EFL Teachers and the level of English performance of Stage 6 students.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that all ethical issues were addressed in this study. All respondents received an informed consent form prior to answering the survey. The consent form discussed their role in the study, its commitment to confidentiality and anonymity, and the assurance that all respondents could discontinue participation at any time. The research instruments did not have their names, but the data was stored and saved securely. No information was shared or given to other individuals not working with the study. After the completion of the study, all data was stored securely and couldn't be accessed by anyone other than the researcher.

Results and Discussions

This section presents the data gathered in connection with the problem of the investigation, analyzes the data through the identified statistical tools, and interprets the results derived from the analysis. All these procedures were done per the specific objectives of the study

Table 1

Level of Instructional Practices of EFL Teachers in the Area of Assessment of Learning

Items	Mean	Interpretation
In my EFL classes, I		
1. give individual formative assessment on the focused skill on daily basis	4.00	High Level
2. give more than one activity to increase students language proficiency	4.11	High Level
3. use open-ended questions to ignite creativity of response	4.09	High Level
4. provide daily homework for enrichment and skills refinement	3.87	High Level

5. use full English instructions during assessment	3.99	High Level
6. make use of performance criteria or rubrics	4.18	High Level
7. employ assessment as student-centered rather than content-centered	4.24	High Level
Overall Mean	4.07	High Level

Table 1 presents the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers in the area of assessment of learning. As shown in the table, an overall mean of 4.07 was obtained with a verbal interpretation of high level. The highest item was in no. 7 on employing student-centered rather than content-centered assessment, obtaining a mean score of 4.24 or high level. Conversely, the lowest mean score obtained was 3.87, interpreted as a high level which is the item no. 4, providing daily homework for enrichment and skills refinement. Possible reasons behind the results could be that teachers are not required to give students daily homework, students may be overwhelmed with their workload, they may not see the immediate value of homework, or they do not receive timely feedback on their assignments, which results in a poor assignment completion rate.

On a more positive note, homework worked as an effective study tool for scheduled exams, and those who did well on assigned homework performed significantly better (Planchard, 2015). **It allows students to reinforce and practice the concepts learned in class, helping them better understand and internalize the material. Students can solidify their knowledge and develop a deeper understanding of the subject by practicing regularly.**

Table 2

Level of Instructional Practices of EFL Teachers in the Area of ICT Integration

Items	Mean	Interpretation
In my EFL classes, I...		
1. use online games such as bamboo, word wall, blookey, quizzes etc. to widen students' vocabulary	3.91	High Level
2. use audios and videos for listening and speaking lessons	4.11	High Level
3. integrate writing applications such as padlet, google classroom etc. to assess students' writing skills	4.32	High Level
4. use various platforms (e.g. LMS, Edmodo, google drive) to provide additional EFL learning resources	3.68	High Level
5. encourage students in class to search for relevant information on the Internet	3.81	High Level
6. permit students to use various platforms for their project presentations	4.14	High Level
7. make use of audio books or book software to teach reading interactively	3.82	High Level
Overall Mean	3.97	High Level

The data presented in table 2 shows the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers in the area of ICT integration. The table shows the overall mean of 3.97 with a verbal interpretation of high level. Item no. 3, which is on integrating writing applications such as Padlet, Google Classroom, etc., to assess students' writing skills, got the highest mean score of 4.32 or higher level. The lowest mean score obtained was 3.68 in item no. 4, interpreted as high level which is on using various platforms like LMS, Edmodo, and Google Drive to provide additional EFL learning resources. Although it is the lowest mean, its interpretation is still high level indicating that teachers generally perceive this aspect positively. This means that most EFL teachers use multiple platforms for learning resources in teaching, which can be seen as a positive indicator of educators going above and beyond traditional methods. Diverse learning resources are necessary to maximize learning especially for students who are born and grown in a digital era (Wu and Hsu, 2014). These students are now immersed in a world where smartphones, tablets, and computers are commonplace from a young age. This constant technological access has shaped students' experiences, behaviors, and expectation which calls the need for teachers to be technologically savvy.

Table 3

Level of Instructional Practices of EFL Teachers in the Area of Differentiated Instructions

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As an EFL teacher, I		
1. design content that vary in difficulty	4.24	High Level
2. provide activities that require varied outputs	4.31	High Level
3. deliver lessons in different ways/approaches	4.74	Very High Level
4. change the learning environment based on the learning preferences of the students (seating arrangement, groupings, etc.)	4.38	High Level
5. conduct diagnostic tests and group students according to their level	4.11	High Level
6. allow peer-feedbacking in any classroom performances	3.75	High Level
7. facilitate and offer support or advice when needed	4.73	Very High

Overall Mean	4.32	Level High Level
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Table 3 presents the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers in terms of differentiated instructions. As shown in the table, an overall mean of 4.32 was obtained with a verbal interpretation of very high level. The highest mean was in item no. 3 which is delivering lessons in different ways/approaches obtaining a mean score of 4.74 or high school. On the other hand, item no. 6 got the lowest mean score of 3.75, interpreted as high level, which is on allowing peer-feedbacking in any classroom performances. **The results could be caused by various factors, such as students feeling uncomfortable giving or receiving feedback from their peers, lack of clarity on effectively providing feedback or a perception that peer feedback may not be as beneficial as other forms of assessment or feedback.** This supports Wang (2015) that EFL students lack confidence in whether they can provide specific feedback or they struggle to give detailed feedback to their peers. Despite the benefits of peer feedback, students in Hong Kong prefer teacher feedback to peer feedback. Students perceive teachers as qualified and superior to provide them with valuable comments (Bijami et al., 2023).

Table 4

Level of English Performance of Stage 6 Students in the First Term for the School Year 2022-2023

Variable	N	Mean	Interpretation
English Performance	2492	6.85	Clever

Table 4 presents the level of English performance of stage 6 students in the first term for the school year 2022-2023. As presented in table 9, the English performance of stage 6 students in the 1st term for the school year 2022-2023 obtained a mean score or 6.85, interpreted as clever. When students receive a score that falls between good and average, it suggests that they have a strong grasp of English concepts and skills. However, it also indicates that they may struggle with communication skills. This could mean that while they have a good understanding of grammar, vocabulary, and reading comprehension, they may face challenges in effectively expressing their thoughts and ideas verbally or in writing. Improving communication skills can help bridge this gap and enable students to fully showcase their knowledge and understanding of the English language. **There are** factors are affecting the students' English performance, preventing them from reaching a higher level of proficiency. These hindrances could be external or internal factors that impact their language learning process, such as limited exposure to English-speaking environments, insufficient resources, and lack of motivation, ineffective teaching methods, or any other challenges hindering their progress.

According to Nguyen et al. (2021), the more English exposure students have in school, the better is their language competence. This could be addressed only when the medium of instruction is in English. However, EFL teacher can always encourage students to speak English to their friends, read English books or watch English movies to increase the frequency of getting exposed to the English language.

Table 5

Difference in the Level of Instructional Practices of EFL Teachers in the Area of Assessment of Learning When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Length of Service	Shorter	40	37.41	676.50	0.048		Significant
	Longer	45	47.97				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	56	43.34	793.00	0.859	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	29	42.34				
Age	Younger	42	41.90	857.00	0.684		Not Significant
	Older	43	44.07				
Sex	Male	22	44.77	654.00	0.694		Not Significant
	Female	63	42.38				

Table 5 shows the difference of the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers in terms of area of assessment when grouped and compared according to length of service, highest educational attainment, age, and sex. As to length of service, the shorter group got a mean rank of 37.41 and 47.97 for the longer group with a Mann Whitney result of 676.50 and a p-value of 0.048. As to highest educational attainment, the lower group and the higher group obtained a mean rank of 43.34 and 42.34 respectively with a Mann Whitney result of 793.00 and a p-value of 0.859. Moreover, age in younger and older groups got a mean rank of 41.90 and 44.77 with a Mann Whitney result of 857.00 and a p-value of 0.684. Furthermore, male, and female groups got a mean rank of 44.77 and 42.38 with a Mann Whitney statistic of 654.00 and a p-value of 0.694.

The Mann Whitney U-Test result shows that among the aforementioned variables, only the length of service was interpreted as “significant”, and all the other variables were interpreted as “not significant. Thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of EFL teachers’ instructional practices when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables was accepted. Based on the findings, it could be inferred that there are many factors that **influence instructional practices. These may include training, professional development, teaching philosophies, and student needs. These factors shape instructional practices rather than the isolated variables of length of service, highest educational attainment, age, or sex.** Although the study Kavinda (2014) found that teachers who have been teaching for many years have established routines and effective techniques, **it still does not guarantee a significant difference in instructional practices. Factors such as professional development opportunities, exposure to new teaching methodologies, and personal teaching style can greatly influence instructional practices regardless of the teacher's length of service. Teachers should focus on continuous professional development and staying updated with the latest research and advancements in EFL education.**

Table 6
Difference in the Level of Instructional Practices of EFL Teachers in the Area of ICT Integration When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Length of Service	Shorter	40	42.94	897.50	0.982		Not Significant
	Longer	45	43.06				
Highest Attainment	Lower	56	44.93	704.00	0.314	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	29	39.28				
Age	Younger	42	44.04	859.50	0.700		Not Significant
	Older	43	41.99				
Sex	Male	22	43.36	685.00	0.936		Not Significant
	Female	63	42.87				

Table 6 reveals the difference in the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers in the area of ICT integration when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. As can be seen in Table 38; it is revealed that in length of service the shorter and the longer groups obtained a mean rank of 42.94 and 43.06 respectively with Mann Whitney statistics result of 897.50 and a p-value of 0.850 interpreted as “Not Significant”. As to highest educational attainment, the lower group got a mean rank of 44.93 and in higher group with 39.28 with a Mann Whitney result of 704.00 and a p-value of 314. Moreover, the younger and the older groups got a mean rank of 44.04 and 41.99 with a Mann Whitney result of 859.50 with a p-value of 0.700. As to sex, male and female groups got a mean score of 43.36 and 42.87 respectively with a Mann Whitney result of 685.00 and a p-value of 0.936. Obviously, the variables length of service, highest educational background, age, and sex do not have bearing on the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers in terms of ICT integration. Teachers who have longer teaching experience, older in the profession, or with higher educational attainment does not guarantee to be proficient or excellent in integrating ICT in the classroom. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of EFL teachers’ instructional practices in terms of ICT integration when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables was hereby accepted.

This emphasizes the importance of providing equal opportunities and resources for all EFL teachers, regardless of these demographic factors, to enhance their ability to integrate technology effectively in the classroom. Alemu (2015) stated that ICT integration might be new to some teachers; hence it must take time for them to learn and apply ICT skills into the teaching and learning process. It is also important to acknowledge the potential variation in teaching styles, approaches, and preferences that may exist within each group. Additionally, further research and studies might be necessary to explore other factors influencing ICT integration among EFL teachers.

Table 7
Difference in the Level of Instructional Practices of EFL Teachers in the Area Differentiated Instruction When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
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Length of Service	Shorter	40	44.58	837.00	0.576		Not Significant
	Longer	45	41.60				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	56	40.57	676.00	0.203	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	29	47.69				
Age	Younger	42	42.65	888.50	0.898		Not Significant
	Older	43	43.34				
Sex	Male	22	46.43	617.50	0.445		Not Significant
	Female	63	41.80				

Table 7 shows the difference of the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers in terms of differentiated instruction when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. As of length of service, the shorter and longer groups obtained a mean rank of 44.58 and 41.60 respectively with a Mann Whitney result of 837.00 and a p-value of 0.576. As to highest educational attainment, the lower group got a mean rank of 40.57 and the higher group got a mean rank of 47.69 with a Mann Whitney statistic of 676.00 with a p-value of 0.203. In addition, the younger and older groups as to age obtained a mean rank of 42.65 and 43.34 respectively with a Mann Whitney result of 888.50 and a p-value of 0.898. Moreover, the male and female groups as to sex got a mean rank of 46.43 and 41.80 respectively and Mann Whitney statistics result of 617.50 and a p-value of 0.445. The Mann Whitney U-test result shows that there is no significant difference between the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers in terms of differentiated instructions when grouped and compared according to length of service, highest educational attainment, age, and sex.

Thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of EFL teachers' instructional practices when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables was hereby accepted. This study demonstrates that when considering differentiated instruction in EFL teaching, the level of instructional practices does not significantly differ based on length of service, highest educational attainment, age, or sex. It emphasizes the importance of providing continuous professional development opportunities and support for all EFL teachers, regardless of their background, to enhance their skills in implementing effective differentiated instruction strategies.

However, this contradicts the study of Siam and Al-Natour (2016), that students who were trained in a differential methodology did not perform or achieve any better. It can be inferred that the implementation of differentiated instruction depends on a teacher's overall pedagogical knowledge, adaptability, ongoing professional development, and ability to meet diverse student needs, regardless of these demographic variables. Teachers can adapt differentiated method as an additional learner requirement and must be tailored according to the needs of each student (Suprayogi & Valcke, 2016).

Table 8

Relationship Between the Level of Instructional Practices of EFL Teachers and the Level of English Performance of Stage 6 Students

Variables	<i>rho</i>	p-value	Sig level	Interpretation
Level of Instructional Practices of EFL Teachers	-0.021	0.845	0.05	Not Significant
Level of English Performance of Stage 6 Students				

In table 8, it summarizes the relationship between the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers and the level of English performance of Stage 6 students. The level of significance is 0.05 with a p-value of 0.845 interpreted as "Not Significant" and rho of -0.021. This simply indicates that there is no significant relationship between the level of instructional practices of EFL teachers and the level of English performance of Stage 6 students.

Thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the level of EFL teachers' instructional practices and the level of English performance of Stage 6 students was accepted. This means that the lack of a significant relationship between the level of EFL teachers' instructional practices and the level of English performance of students can be attributed to various factors. The instructional practices employed by EFL teachers may vary due to factors such as teaching experience, educational background, and professional development opportunities. While some teachers may use innovative and effective instructional techniques, others may rely on more traditional methods. Consequently, the heterogeneous nature of instructional practices could contribute to the absence of a significant relationship between these practices and student English performance. It is also

important to note that language acquisition is a complex process influenced by multiple factors, including individual student characteristics, motivation, exposure to the language outside of the classroom, and cultural background. While EFL teachers play a crucial role in providing instruction and creating a conducive learning environment, they cannot solely determine the success or failure of students' English performance. The study of Ikram et. al (2020) supports that teacher's way of instructional has a significant effect on student's achievement. However, the instructional practices alone may not be the sole determinant of students' English performance English language acquisition is a complex process influenced by various factors.

Conclusions

EFL teachers' levels of instructional practices were found to be high. The level of English performance of Stage 6 students during the First Term of School Year 2022-2023 was "clever". No significant difference exists in the levels of EFL teachers' instructional practices when grouped according to variables. No significant difference likewise exists between the level of EFL teachers' instructional practices and the English performance of Stage 6 students. The high levels of EFL teachers' instructional practices indicate a strong commitment to teaching excellence, which ultimately benefits EFL students and all stakeholders. The clever performance of Stage 6 students in English indicates a high level of proficiency, creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving in their use of the English language during the specified term. The data collected from the survey in this study provided a large amount of information regarding the professional development and instructional practices of EFL teachers concerning students' English performance. Based on the results, the following recommendations are made: 1) Separate the trainings or workshops that focus only on instructing EFL students; 2) Increase the number of English classes per week, providing more exposure and communication practice with students to help improve English performance; and 3) Conduct follow up studies covering more teachers, not limited to one school, but include different schools and language centers, to validate the results.

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